

Saponin of *Aesculus pinduana* Leaves

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AESCULUS Linn. is a genus of Hippocastanaceae family comprising 25 species of trees and shrubs distributed in Asia, Europe and America. *A. indica* and *A. pinduana* Wall. (syn. *A. assamica* Griff.) are the two species found in India. The 50% ethanolic extract of the fruits of *A. indica* is reported to possess diuretic activity¹ and the oil from the seeds is used in rheumatism. The fruits and bark of *A. hippocastanum* are useful in the treatment of fevers and as antiperiodic².

The reported diuretic activity and effect on cardiovascular system¹ of the ethanolic extract of *A. pinduana*, together with the medicinal uses and the interesting compounds reported³ from the genus prompted us to take up a detailed chemical investigation of the plant.

Experimental

Concentrated ethanolic extract of dried and powdered leaves (900 g) of *A. pinduana* was successively macerated with petroleum ether (4 × 250 ml), benzene (4 × 200 ml) and ethylacetate (4 × 200 ml) and the residual alcoholic extract was processed for saponin by the usual process to yield amorphous powder (12 g). The saponin (8 g) was acid hydrolysed and the sapogenins (5.3 g) thus obtained were subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (400 g) affording the following compounds.

The CHCl₃-MeOH (19 : 1) elution of the column gave an LB positive white compound (50 mg), m.p., 325-326°, (α)_D+29.5° (pyridine), M⁺, 490, analysed for C₂₀H₃₀O₆; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3370 (OH) and 1645 cm⁻¹ (double bond); MS m/e 490 (M⁺), 282, 264, 246, 215, 207, 197 and 189; penta acetate m.p. 152-155°. These spectral data suggested its identity as barringtogenol-C³ confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with the same solvent gave another LB positive white compound (150 mg), m.p. 262-265°, (α)_D+9.2°, M⁺, 572, C₂₅H₃₆O₆; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3390 (OH), 1695 (CO), 1640 and 1265 cm⁻¹; MS m/e 572 (3%, M⁺), 364(5), 282(3), 246(3.5), 215(16), 207(35), 197(5), 189(32) and 83(100). On acetylation with C₆H₅N-Ac₂O at room temperature it gave triacetyl derivative m.p., 280-282°, (α)_D+19.5°, C₄₁H₆₂O₉. On alkaline hydrolysis the compound gave barringtogenol-C, m.p. 325-326°, M⁺, 490 and tiglic acid (glc). The close resemblance of its m.p. and spectral data suggested its identity with 21-tiglate barringtogenol-C⁴.

The final elution of the column afforded LB positive white compound needles from MeOH, m.p. 241-245°; M⁺, 588, C₂₈H₃₆O₇; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3400 (OH), 1700 (CO) and 1645 cm⁻¹ (double bond); MS m/e 588 (M⁺), 364, 282, 246, 223, 215, 207, 197, 175 and 83 (base peak). On alkaline hydrolysis it gave protoaescigenin and tiglic acid. These data suggested its identity as protoaescigenin-21-tiglate⁵.

In the aqueous hydrolysate of the saponin, glucuronic acid, glucose and galactose were identified as sugars (co-pc).

The petroleum ether soluble fraction (15 g) of the alcoholic extract of *A. pinduana* leaves was chromatographed over silica gel (500 g). Elution of the column with *n*-hexane-benzene (3 : 1) afforded crystalline product, m.p. 84-85° which was identified as *n*-hentriacontanol by comparison with an authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with the same solvent gave an LB positive crystalline compound, m.p. 190-192°, (α)_D+90°, M⁺, 426, analysed for C₃₀H₅₀O; ν_{max}^{KBr} 3350 (OH), 825 and 813 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond), monoacetate, m.p. 232-235°. On the basis of spectral studies the compound was identified as β-amyrin and was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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**O,O-Diethyl Phosphono/Phosphonothioyl
N,N-Dialkyldithiocarbamates**

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THE dithiocarbamate derivatives find their use as fungicides and pesticides¹. Besides their biological significance, the dithiocarbamate ligands possess a structural importance too. They can form either monodentate or bidentate metal complexes. In earlier communications²⁻⁵ we reported a number of organometallic compounds of N,N-dialkyl and N,N-alkylcyclohexyl dithiocarbamates. In all these compounds, the dithiocarbamate ligands are bidentate. In continuation, we report the study of a set

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NOTES

of compounds in which the dithiocarbamate moiety is attached to phosphorus. Thus, a few O,O-diethyl phosphono/phosphonothioyl N,N-dialkyl dithiocarbamates, (I-VI) (A and B), were prepared and studied. Like the dithiocarbamate derivatives, a number of compounds derived from diethoxyphosphoryl chloride and diethoxythiophosphoryl chloride possess insecticidal and pesticidal activities^{6,7}. It is thus likely that the O,O-diethyl phosphono/phosphonothioyl dithiocarbamates would possess considerable biochemical activity.

- I, R=R'=Me; IV, R=Me, R'=cyclohexyl (cyhx);
 II, R=R'=Et; V, R=Et, R'=cyhx A; X=O;
 III, R=R'=i-Pr; VI, R=i-Pr, R'=cyhx B; X=S.

Experimental

Infrared spectra in KBr pellets in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin Elmer 621 Infrared spectrophotometer. The ^1H nmr spectra were recorded at a sweep width of 900 Hz with a Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Chemical shifts are expressed relative to TMS (1% by volume). The uv spectra were recorded in methanol on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, model 554.

Sodium dithiocarbamates were prepared by the method of Klöpping and Kerk⁸. Diethoxyphosphoryl chloride and diethoxythiophosphoryl chloride were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals.

Preparation of the compounds: All the compounds were prepared by a similar procedure. Diethoxyphosphoryl chloride or diethoxythiophosphoryl chloride was stirred with stoichiometric amount of sodium dithiocarbamates in about 100 ml chloroform for about 3 hr at 10°. The dark brown solution was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to about 20 ml. White crystals were obtained by adding petroleum ether (60-80°) to the concentrated filtrate. All the operations were carried out in strictly anhydrous medium.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the analytical data and physical characteristics of the compounds. The compounds are white in colour and soluble in common organic solvents. Although the N,N-alkylcyclohexyldithiocarbamate derivatives are quite stable in air, the corresponding dialkyldithiocarbamate compounds are stable only in inert atmosphere and decompose on standing in air. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solution of these compounds in nitrobenzene were found to be of the order of 0.5 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$. These conductivity results indicate the covalent nature of the compounds and absence of ionic species in solution.

All the reported compounds possess a doublet at $\sim 1000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ region, which supports the monodentate nature of the dithiocarbamate ligands⁹. The thioureide band $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ which absorbs at $\sim 1470 \text{cm}^{-1}$ splits into a doublet, which further supports the monodentate nature of the dithiocarbamate ligand¹⁰.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND ANALYTICAL DATA

Compound	Yield %	m.p. °C	Conductivity Λ_M $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				S	N
I(A)	50	118	0.50	24.81 (24.90)	5.86 (5.44)
II(A)	53	124	0.50	22.38 (22.45)	4.85 (4.91)
III(A)	55	118	0.52	20.52 (20.44)	4.55 (4.47)
IV(A)	65	159	0.54	19.75 (19.69)	4.22 (4.30)
V(A)	62	170	0.50	18.80 (18.87)	4.21 (4.12)
VI(A)	60	167	0.58	18.06 (18.13)	3.81 (3.96)
I(B)	45	110	0.52	23.51 (23.44)	5.07 (5.12)
II(B)	43	119	0.56	21.35 (21.26)	4.59 (4.65)
III(B)	47	114	0.54	19.52 (19.45)	4.18 (4.25)
IV(B)	64	152	0.54	18.85 (18.76)	4.16 (4.10)
V(B)	60	163	0.56	18.11 (18.42)	3.86 (3.94)
VI(B)	66	143	0.50	17.40 (17.84)	3.69 (3.79)

TABLE 2—RELEVANT SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	IR (cm ⁻¹) ^a			¹ H NMR (δ) ^b		
	ν(C=O)	ν(C=N)	ν(P=X)	-OCH ₃	N-CH ₃	N-CH ₃
I(A)	990, 1010 (s)	1450, 1465 (s)	1325 (m)	4.35 (m)	—	3.34 (s)
II(A)	995, 1015 (s)	1460, 1470 (s)	1350 (m)	4.28 (m)	3.74 (q) J=6.8 Hz	—
III(A)	1005, 1020 (s)	1455, 1470 (s)	1320 (m)	4.22 (m)	—	—
IV(A)	1000, 1015 (s)	1460, 1475 (s)	1340 (m)	4.25 (m)	—	3.28 (s)
V(A)	995, 1010 (s)	1465, 1475 (s)	1325 (m)	4.28 (m)	3.70 (q) J=7.0 Hz	—
VI(A)	1000, 1025 (s)	1450, 1470 (s)	1350 (m)	4.30 (m)	—	—
I(B)	990, 1015 (s)	1455, 1475 (s)	720 (m)	4.32 (m)	—	3.33 (s)
II(B)	990, 1010 (s)	1460, 1470 (s)	735 (m)	4.30 (m)	3.72 (q) J=7.0 Hz	—
III(B)	1005, 1025 (s)	1450, 1465 (s)	725 (m)	4.25 (m)	—	—
IV(B)	1005, 1020 (s)	1450, 1470 (s)	725 (m)	4.28 (m)	—	3.34 (s)
V(B)	995, 1015 (s)	1455, 1470 (s)	730 (m)	4.30 (m)	3.75 (q) J=6.8 Hz	—
VI(B)	1000, 1025 (s)	1460, 1475 (s)	725 (m)	4.32 (m)	—	—

a—(s) strong, (m) medium.

b—(s) singlet, (q) quartet, (m) multiplet.

The ν(P=O) stretching frequency occurs around 1300 cm⁻¹ and ν(P=S) near 760 cm⁻¹^{11,12}. Absorptions owing to ν(C-O-P) and ν(P-S) stretching frequencies occur at ~1110 and ~475 cm⁻¹, respectively^{11,13}.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded in CDCl₃. Whereas the resonance signals due to the C-CH₃ (in EtO), -N-CH₃, -N-CH₂ and N-CH₃ groups are clearly separated from each other, those of the -CH₃ (in EtO and Et) and cyhx protons overlap with each other. Thus a multiplet appeared in the region δ 1.1-1.7 and the CH₃ and cyhx groups could not be identified separately. Nevertheless, the spectra show no trace of free ligands indicating that the compounds do not dissociate upon dissolution. Relevant spectral data are given in Table 2.

Absorptions in the uv region, arising out of the internal transitions among the chromophoric groups present in the compounds, were studied in methanol. An intense band near 235 nm arises due to the π→π* transitions of the P=O group. In case of the corresponding thio derivatives, the P=S group absorbs at ~220 nm. A shoulder band at ~280 nm appears due to the π→π* transitions of the N=C=S group in the dithiocarbamate moiety¹⁴.

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